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Diffusion Rate of Resonant Electron's at High Latitudes

By

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Diffusion rates are strongly dependent on the ratio between the electron plasma and gyro-frequencies. For conditions typical of storm times, diffusion rates are extremely sensitive to energy and become ineffective above 3 MeV. At energies below 100 keV pitch angle, diffusion approaches strong diffusion loss to the atmosphere, while loss at higher energies is much weaker. Resonant interaction between particles and waves violates the conservation of the magnetic moment and causes diffusion in energy and pitch angle of the interacting particles. If wave diffusion is weak then waves are not amplified to the extent as required but when diffusion is moderate and strong, we get intense waves at the receiver. These waves propagate from one hemisphere to another hemisphere crossing the geomagnetic equator bringing valuable information regarding particle distribution in the ionosphere and magnetosphere. Kinds of observations as well as theoretical work done in the field support our result. In this paper, we compute diffusion's rate of electrons energy interacting with coherent/incoherent whistler mode VLF waves at high latitudes. Herein we extend the theory of Summers et al (2007).

Keywords: VLF waves, Cyclotron interactions, Gyro frequency, Diffusion rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Whistler mode waves play an important role in the earth's magnetosphere through hitting of relativistic energetic electrons as well as causing their precipitation into the lower ionosphere. In this case, electron motion in a coherent packet of Whistler mode wave propagating along the direction of an ambient magnetic field is studied (VII B). V is velocity of the particle and B is geomagnetic field. The parametric dependence of the diffusion coefficient $D(\alpha)$, on ambient plasma density (N , el./cm³), magnitude of wave field $2fB$ and field strength (B) have been studied by Singh. They have shown that significant pitch angle diffusion occurs for the earth radiation belt electrons with energies from a few KeV up to a few MeV. Herein, the variation of diffusion coefficient $D(\alpha)$, on frequency of the whistler wave (f) as well as wave magnetic field (B_w) are studied. Wave-particle interactions play a fundamental role in radiation belt electron dynamics; see the reviews by Gendrin (2001), Horne (2002), and Thorne et al, (2005a). Gyro-resonant interactions are associated with high-frequency waves in the range $0.1\Omega_{O^+} < \omega < 0.8|\Omega_e|$, where Ω_{O^+} is the oxygen ion gyrofrequency and $|\Omega_e|$ is the electron gyrofrequency. Waves in this frequency range include whistler-mode chorus, plasma-spheric hiss and electromagnetic ion cyclotron (EMIC) waves. Drift-resonant interactions are associated with ULF waves at lower frequencies. Energy diffusion due to cyclotron resonance with chorus waves is a viable mechanism for generating relativistic electrons (>1 MeV) in the outer zone during storms (Summers et al., 1998, 2002, 2004a, 2004b; Roth et al., 1999; Summers and Ma, 2000; Horne et al., 2005a; Thorne et al., 2005a; Varotsou et al., 2005). Radial (cross-L) diffusion driven by enhanced ULF waves has also been cited as an effective mechanism for generating storm time relativistic electrons (Hudson et al., 2001; Elkington et al., 2003). While radial diffusion is effective for energizing electrons outside geosynchronous orbit, there is evidence that an additional local acceleration mechanism also participate (e.g., O'Brien et al., 2003; Miyoshi et al., 2003, 2004; Shprits and Thorne, 2004; Iles et al., 2006). Both Horne et al. (2005b) and Shprits et al. (2006a) demonstrated that ULF wave-driven radial diffusion could not explain the formation of the new radiation belt in the "slot" region following the 2003 Halloween storm. Horne et al. (2005b) and Shprits et al. (2006a) found that energy diffusion driven by whistler-mode waves could explain the gradual build up of electron fluxes to energies of several MeV in this slot region normally devoid of energetic electrons. Gyro-resonant interactions with whistler-mode chorus also provide a process for electron loss from the radiation belts. Electron cyclotron resonance with chorus can cause pitch angle scattering into the loss cone and subsequent loss to the atmosphere (Horne and Thorne, 2003; Summers et al., 2005; Thorne et al., 2005b). EMIC waves and plasma-spheric hiss can also contribute to the scattering loss

of radiation belt electrons (Summers and Thorne, 2003; Summers et al., 2005; Meredith et al., 2006). Magnetopause shadowing, or other processes including radial diffusion, may additionally contribute to the loss of radiation belt electrons. A broad discussion of the issues of radiation belt electron transport, acceleration and loss is provided collectively in the papers by Li and Temerin (2001), Friedel et al. (2002), O' Brien et al. (2003), Green and Kivelson (2004), Green et al. (2005), and Thorne et al. (2005a), see also Summers et al. (2007). When wave particle interactions take place in the magnetosphere, wave growth/energy/diffusion of energetic electrons takes place. In this case either the waves are amplified or absorbed. It is clear from the literature that further work is needed to quantify electron acceleration and loss processes in the radiation belts. The aim of the present work (Summers et al., 2007) is to apply quasi-linear diffusion theory to quantify cyclotron resonant interactions of radiation belt electrons with whistler-mode chorus, plasma-spheric hiss, and EMIC waves. We use quasi-linear theory to investigate the average properties of the cyclotron resonant diffusion process. Nonlinear effects including phenomena such as phase trapping are therefore not included and are beyond the scope of our investigation. Many workers of Summers et al (2005, 2007) derived readily computable formulae for the quasi-linear diffusion coefficients for cyclotron resonance with field-aligned (R-mode or L-mode) electromagnetic waves. In order to determine the rates of momentum, diffusion and pitch angle diffusion appropriate to the Earth's assumed dipole magnetic field, we compute energy diffusion coefficient for energetic electrons interacting with coherent/incoherent whistler mode VLF waves and find that coherence is more important in wave particle interaction than incoherence to diffuse energetic electrons into the loss cone which amplify VLF waves at low latitude, along with D-E region perturbation, X-rays and aurorae. In this paper, we study VLF wave growth of interaction between waves of 3, 4, 5 KHz at different L- shells. Herein we extend the theory of Summers et al (2007).

2. METHOD OF CALCULATION AND ENERGY DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS

We assume infinite, homogeneous, collision-less plasma immersed in a uniform, static magnetic field $B_0 = B_0 \hat{e}_z$, in the presence of superposed electromagnetic waves (Inan, 1977). We use quasi-linear diffusion theory to describe the effects of the waves on the particles in terms of a kinetic equation for the gyrophase-averaged phase-space density ρ . Ensemble averaging of the wave fields is carried out. The relativistic quasi-linear diffusion equation for ρ , in the limit of gyro-resonant diffusion, can be written in the form [e.g., Melrose, 1980], Summers et al (2007).

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\sin \alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(D_{\alpha\alpha} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} \right) + \frac{1}{\sin \alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(D_{\alpha p} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial p} \right) + \frac{1}{p^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(p^2 D_{p\alpha} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} \right) + \frac{1}{p^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(p^2 D_{pp} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial p} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $D_{\alpha\alpha}$, $D_{\alpha p} = D_{p\alpha}$ and D_{pp} are the diffusion coefficients which depend on the properties of the waves; $p = \gamma m_\sigma v$ is the momentum of the particle of species σ , rest mass m_σ and speed v ; $\gamma = (1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2})^{-1/2}$ is the Lorentz factor (c is the speed of light); α is the pitch angle of the particle, and t denotes time. In the present study we treat only the special case of electromagnetic waves propagating parallel or antiparallel to the background magnetic field B_0 . We assume that the R-mode ($s=1$) and L-mode ($s=-1$) waves each have the Gaussian spectral density,

$$W_s(f) = \frac{|\Delta B_s|^2}{8\pi} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{1}{\delta f} e^{-\left(\frac{f-f_m}{f}\right)^2}, \quad (2)$$

With

$$\rho = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \left[\text{erf} \left(\frac{f_m - f_1}{\delta f} \right) + \text{erf} \left(\frac{f_2 - f_m}{\delta f} \right) \right], \quad (3)$$

Where f_1 is the lower frequency limit, f_2 is the upper frequency limit, f_m is the frequency of maximum wave power, δf is a measure of the bandwidth, and erf is the error function. The wave spectral density (2) has been normalized, so that (Summers et al, 2007).

$$\frac{|\Delta B_s|^2}{8\pi} = \int_{f_1}^{f_2} \bar{W}_s(f) df \quad (4)$$

Where $|\Delta B_s|^2$ is the mean wave amplitude.

Following the study of Summers et al (2005, 2007), we can now express the diffusion coefficients for the particle species σ as follows:

$$D_{\alpha\alpha} = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\Omega_\sigma^2}{|\Omega_e|} \frac{1}{(E+1)^2} \sum_s \sum_j \frac{R \left(1 - \frac{x_j \cos \alpha}{y_j \beta}\right)^2 |dx_j/dy_j|}{\delta x |\beta \cos \alpha - dx_j/dy_j|} e^{-\left(\frac{x_j - x_m}{\delta x}\right)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{D_{\alpha p}}{p} = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\Omega_\sigma^2}{|\Omega_e|} \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{\sin \alpha}{(E+1)^2} \sum_s \sum_j \frac{R \left(\frac{x_j}{y_j}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x_j \cos \alpha}{y_j \beta}\right)^2 |dx_j/dy_j|}{\delta x |\beta \cos \alpha - dx_j/dy_j|} e^{-\left(\frac{x_j - x_m}{\delta x}\right)^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{D_{pp}}{p^2} = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\Omega_\sigma^2}{|\Omega_e|} \frac{1}{\beta^2} \frac{\sin^2 \alpha}{(E+1)^2} \sum_s \sum_j \frac{R \left(\frac{x_j}{y_j}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{x_j \cos \alpha}{y_j \beta}\right)^2 |dx_j/dy_j|}{\delta x |\beta \cos \alpha - dx_j/dy_j|} e^{-\left(\frac{x_j - x_m}{\delta x}\right)^2} \quad (7)$$

Where we have introduced the dimensionless variables,

$$x = \frac{f}{|\Omega_e|}, \quad y = \frac{ck}{|\Omega_e|} \quad (8)$$

And E is the dimensionless particle kinetic energy given by

$$E = E_k / (m_\sigma c^2) = \gamma - 1; \beta = \frac{v}{c} = [E(E+2)]^{1/2} / (E+1); |\Omega_e| = e |B_0| / (m_e c)$$

is the non-relativistic electron gyrofrequency, where e is the unit charge; $|\Omega_\sigma| = q |B_0| / (m_\sigma c)$ is the non-relativistic particle gyrofrequency, where q is the particle charge; $R = |\Delta B_s|^2 / B_0^2$ is the ratio of the energy density of the turbulent magnetic field to that of the background field, i.e., the relative wave power; $x_m = \frac{f_m}{|\Omega_e|}$,

$\delta x = \frac{\delta f}{|\Omega_e|}$; and the derivative $dx_j/dy_j = dx(y_j)/dy$ is determined from the appropriate dispersion relation. In

(5) – (7) the summations are carried out over the wave modes specified by $s = 1$ (R-mode) and $s = -1$ (L mode), and over the resonant roots f_j, k_j corresponding to each wave mode. As well as satisfying the relevant dispersion equation, the resonant frequency f_j and corresponding resonant wave number k_j (where $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$) satisfy the Doppler gyro-resonance condition, which, for electrons or protons, can be expressed as (Summers et al, 2007).

$$y = \frac{x + a}{\beta \cos \alpha} \quad (9)$$

Where

$$a = \frac{s\lambda}{\gamma} \quad (10)$$

Here, $\lambda = -1$ corresponds to electrons and $\lambda = \varepsilon$ to protons, with $\varepsilon = m_e/m_p$, where m_e is the electron rest mass and m_p the proton rest mass. As in the work of Summers (2005), we restrict the wave frequency f_j to be always positive, and we take a positive wave number ($k_j > 0$) to represent a forward propagating wave and negative wave number ($k_j < 0$) to represent a backward wave. The classical theory of waves in uniform cold plasma is given, for instance, by Stix [1992]. The dispersion relations for R-mode ($s = 1$) or L-mode ($s = -1$) waves propagating parallel or antiparallel to a uniform magnetic field in a cold, multi-ion (H+, He+, O+) plasma are

$$\frac{y^2}{x^2} = 1 + \frac{1}{\alpha^* x} \left(\frac{1}{s-x} - \frac{\varepsilon\eta_1}{x+s\varepsilon} - \frac{\varepsilon\eta_2}{4x+s\varepsilon} - \frac{\varepsilon\eta_3}{16x+s\varepsilon} \right) \quad (11)$$

Where

$$\alpha^* = \Omega_e^2 / f_{pe}^2 \quad (12)$$

is a cold-plasma parameter; $f_{pe} = (4\pi N_0 e^2 / m_e)^{1/2}$ is the electron plasma frequency where

N_0 is the electron number density; $\eta_1 = N_1 / N_0$, $\eta_2 = N_2 / N_0$, and $\eta_3 = N_3 / N_0$, where N_1, N_2 and N_3 denote the hydrogen (H+), helium (He+), and oxygen (O+) ion number densities, respectively. The fractional ion compositions satisfy $\eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_3 = 1$, by charge neutrality. In the special case of a hydrogen plasma ($\eta_1 = 1$, $\eta_2 = \eta_3 = 0$), equations (11) reduce to the form (Summers et al, 2007),

$$\frac{y^2}{x^2} = 1 - \frac{b}{(x-s)(x+s\varepsilon)}, \quad (13)$$

Where

$$b = (1 + \varepsilon) / \alpha^*. \quad (14)$$

The parameter α^* , defined by (12), plays an important role in cold-plasma theory and can be written as $\alpha^* = 9.722 \times 10^{-6} B_0^2 / N_0$, with B_0 (nT) and N_0 (cm^{-3}). If we adopt the Earth's equatorial dipole value for B_0 , namely $B_0 = 3.12 \times 10^4 / L^3$ (nT), then α^* can be expressed as

$$\alpha^* = \frac{9.464 \times 10^3}{L^6 N_0}, \quad (15)$$

With N_0 (cm^{-3}).

Direct observations of whistler-induced electron precipitation on rockets and satellites along with indirect ground-based observations have also been reported.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(1) Variation With Frequency:

Fig. 1: Variation of energy diffusion coefficient Dpp (J^2/s) with pitch angle ($^\circ$) at different interacting VLF frequencies, keeping $L=5$, $Bw = 0.001nT$, and wave width 50Hz.

Fig. (1) shows variation of energy diffusion coefficient [Dpp (J^2/S)] with pitch angle at different frequencies. We see that as pitch angle increases energy diffusion coefficient of particles also increases. Moreover this variation is not only pitch angle dependent but frequency dependent also; we see that energy diffusion coefficient is low for all pitch angle ranges for 3 kHz waves and it is high for 5 kHz waves. It is in agreement with works done by various authors in India (Singh DP) as well as Stanford University.

There is a peculiar situation that energy diffusion coefficient increases with pitch angle linearly, i.e. Dpp and pitch angle graph is almost a straight line. Such things appear for all frequencies. We can conclude that large pitch angle and large frequency waves takes effective role in the diffusion of electrons into loss cone. As we have said, this is in agreement with works of large number of whistler mode wave worker. In this case the L -values is taken to be 5 and wave magnetic field $Bw=0.001pT$, the wave width is taken to be 50Hz. (Geomagnetic Latitude $1/L = \cos^2_{50}$) (Inan 1977).

(2) Variation With L-Values:

Fig. 2: Variation of energy diffusion coefficient Dpp (J^2/s) with pitch angle ($^\circ$) at different L -values, keeping interacting frequency 5 kHz, $Bw = 0.01nT$, and wave width 100Hz.

Fig. (2) shows variation of energy diffusion coefficient [D_{pp} (J^{**}/S)] with pitch angle at different L-values. We see that as pitch angle increases energy diffusion coefficient of particles also increases. Moreover, this variation is not only pitch angle dependent but also L-values dependent; we see that energy diffusion coefficient is low for all pitch angle ranges for $L=4$ and it is high for $L=5$. It is in agreement with works done by various authors in India (Singh DP) as well as Stanford University.

There is a peculiar situation that energy diffusion coefficient increases with pitch angle linearly, i.e. D_{pp} and pitch angle graph is almost a straight line. Such things appear for all L-values. We can conclude that large pitch angle and large L-values takes effective role in the diffusion of electrons into loss cone. As we have said, this is in agreement with works of large number of whistler mode wave worker. In this case the VLF frequency value was taken to be 5 kHz, and wave magnetic field $B_w = 0.1$ nT, the wave width was taken to be 100Hz.

(3) Variation With Wave-Magnetic Field (B_w):

Fig. 3: Variation of energy diffusion coefficient D_{pp} (J^{**}/s) with pitch angle ($^\circ$) at different B_w (nT), keeping $L=5$, interacting frequency 5kHz and wave width 100Hz.

Fig. (3) shows variation of energy diffusion coefficient [D_{pp} (J^{**}/S)] with pitch angle at different Wave-Magnetic Field B_w (nT). Moreover, this variation is not only pitch angle dependent but wave magnetic field (B_w) dependent also; we see that energy diffusion coefficient is low for all pitch angle ranges for $B_w=0.001$ nT and it is high for $B_w=0.1$ nT. It is in agreement with works done by various authors in India (Singh DP) as well as Stanford University.

There is a peculiar situation that energy diffusion coefficient increases with pitch angle linearly and decreases also with pitch angle linearly, i.e. D_{pp} and pitch angle graph is almost a straight line for both increasing and decreasing cases of energy diffusion coefficient [D_{pp} (J^{**}/S)] with pitch angle. Such things appear for all B_w values. We can conclude that large pitch angle and large wave-magnetic field [B_w (nT)] takes effective role in the diffusion of electrons into loss cone. As we have said this is in agreement with works of large number of whistler mode wave worker. In this case the VLF frequency value was taken to be 4 kHz and the L-values taken to be 5, the wave width was taken to be 100Hz. Inan (1977) has shown that B_w plays an important role in dragging energetic electrons into the loss cone. In our case also we see that energy diffusion coefficient increases with B_w . So that electrons are lost and we get strong waves at the receiver.

(4) Variation With Wave-Width (Coherence):

Fig.4: Variation of energy diffusion coefficient D_{pp} (J^{**}/s) with L-values at different wave-width ΔF (Hz.), keeping frequency 5 kHz, $B_w = 0.01$ (nT) and Pitch Angle 30° .

Fig. (4) shows variation of energy diffusion coefficient [D_{pp} (J^{**}/S)] with L - values at different wave-width (coherence). Moreover, this variation is not only L - values dependent but wave-width dependent also; we see that energy diffusion coefficient is low at all L -values for wave-width 150Hz. and it is high for 50 Hz. wave-width. It is in agreement with works done by various authors in India (Singh DP) as well as Stanford University.

There is a peculiar situation that energy diffusion coefficient increases exponentially. Such things appear for all wave-width. We can conclude that large L values and large wave-width takes effective role in the diffusion of electrons into loss cone. As we have said this is in agreement with works of large number of whistler mode wave worker. In this case the pitch angle was taken to be 30° and wave magnetic field $B_w = 0.01nT$, the interacting frequency was taken to be 5kHz. (Geomagnetic Latitude $1/L = \cos^2 \theta$). After studying variations of energy diffusion coefficient with wave-width, we see that large wave-width reduces the diffusion. We see that lesser the wave-width (more coherence) than large wave-width (less coherence). Thus we can say that coherent waves play an important role in wave particle interaction and wave amplification.

In the last, it is worthwhile to note that our theoretical $D_{\alpha\alpha}$ values are in agreement with experimental values reported by Davidson and Walt (1977) who have observed $D_{\alpha\alpha}$ values in the range of 0.001 to 0.050. Thus our $D_{\alpha\alpha}$ expression is not only easy to use but correct also.

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